
PUBLIC SATISFACTION MEASUREMENT SYSTEM ON PUBLIC SECTOR ORGANIZATION IN PALEMBANG CITY

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Abstract:

Role of public sector organization in economic development is very important. Public sector serves most administrative activity to public/ people. It is important to measure public satisfaction as a reflection of government's performance. This research proposed a fit model for measure public satisfaction in Palembang City. Public sector in Palembang must have a quality assurance and indicator to measure the public satisfaction. Stage of measurement system must involve the major, internal and eksternal auditor and the public. The most important is that public sector must hire a professional employee that responsive and empathy to public.

Keywords: *Public Satisfaction; Satisfaction Measurement System; Public Sector; Servqual; Quality Assurance.*

Cite This Article: Maya Panorama. (2018). "PUBLIC SATISFACTION MEASUREMENT SYSTEM ON PUBLIC SECTOR ORGANIZATION IN PALEMBANG CITY." *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 5(2), 46-56. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1174105.

1. Introduction

Enactment of Indonesia Number 32, Year 2004 states that regional autonomy has been given authority and flexibility to the region to organize the government. The authority should be used to improve the quality of service and public welfare. It is also emphasized by Mubyarto (in Ratminto, 2005) that the essence of regional autonomy is the transfer of authority over all matters of government to the districts/ municipalities, so that district/ city governments can improve services to the public (more smoothly, easier, faster and more cheap).

Independency self-manage territory, facing the problem where the government should be able to serve the public. Public satisfaction is a condition where the wishes, hopes and needs of the public are fulfilled. A service is considered satisfactory if the service can meet the needs and expectations of the public. Measuring public satisfaction is an important element in providing better, more efficient and more effective service. If people feel dissatisfied with a service provided, then the service can be as ineffective and inefficient. This is especially important for public services

The level of public satisfaction with services is an important factor in developing a system of government service delivery that is responsive to public needs, minimizing cost and time and maximizing the impact of services on target populations. Andaleeb (2001) conducted a study on hospital patients in Bangladesh. The results of the study identified the quality of perceived patient care, including responsiveness, assurance, communication, discipline, and baksheesh. Using factor analysis and multiple regression, found a significant relationship between the five dimensions and patient satisfaction.

The unmeasured and publicized performance of public services will make the public workers feel "nobody-cares-anyway" mentality with their performance and free to do as they please. One of the most important reasons for a system of performance measurement of public services is the source of motivation for the public service/ HR implementers themselves. Such implementers, as well as private sector employees, also need recognition for their performance. If there is no mechanism that shows their work so far, then the implementer has no basis whatsoever to be appreciated: lazy-diligent is the same. (Susanto, 2006)

Monitoring system and measurement of public satisfaction is a systematic process that seeks to measure the extent to which the process of public service activities can be measured and meet the wishes of the public as a service user. Given the absence of a standard system that can be used in assessing the performance of public services, it is necessary to create a system of measurement and evaluation that can be used to assess the extent to which a form of public service can be measured. Next will be analyzed and evaluated whether it is in accordance with the desired by the public, as one manifestation of the formation of accountability of public service executors. Problems that can be formulated from the above background is proposed a public satisfaction measurement system that suitable in public sector organization in Palembang.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Service Quality

According to Lukman (2003), quality can be interpreted as conformity with requirements, with the user or free from damage/ defects. Quality has many different definitions and varies from conventional to more strategic. The conventional definition of quality usually describes the immediate characteristics of a product such as: Performance; Reliability; Easy in use and Aesthetics. The definition of service according to Ivancevich, et.al in Ratminto and Winarsih (2005), service is invisible (invisible) products that involve human endeavors and equipment use. According to Supriyanto and Sugiyanti (2001), service is an effort to help prepare, provide, or take care of the needs of others. The party served is called the public. The form of service may be in the form of real goods, tangible goods or services. Further, Moenir (2002) revealed that the services required by humans are basically 2 (two) of personal service and administrative services. Administrative services are usually associated with large organizations one of which is a public organization so that the services provided are called public services or public services.

Quality of service according to Lukman (2003) is a service activity given to the public in accordance with the principle: cheaper, better, faster, accurate, and friendly, in accordance with public expectations. Furthermore, Lukman (2003) reveals the quality of service

is the service provided to the public in accordance with standardized services that have been standardized as a guide in service delivery. Service standard is a predetermined measure as good service standardization. This standard refers to the Decree of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2017 concerning the Establishment of Top 99 Public Service Innovations Year 2017.

2.2. Public Satisfaction Measurement System

Service quality control is basically the quality control of the work and the process of activities to create public satisfaction made by everyone from every part of the organization. The PDCA cycle approach (Plan Do Check Action) can be used as a model to analyze the process and quality of service. PDCA is a useful tool to make continuous improvement (continuous improvement) without stopping.

A service is considered satisfactory if the service can meet the needs and expectations of the public. Before carrying out the service functions should be known before the wishes and expectations of society so that the function of service can be useful as it should. There are several alternative systems that can be used for monitoring and measuring public satisfaction. This system can be used interchangeably and not focused on one public sector organization only. Many definitions related to customer satisfaction are mentioned by Tjiptono (2004), which cites Day's opinion: satisfaction or dissatisfaction is a public response to a perceived discrepancy/ disconfirmation evaluation between the previous expectations (or other performance norms) and the actual performance of the product perceived by the wearer. Kotler (1994) mentions public satisfaction as: the level of one's feelings after comparing perceived performance (outcome) compared to expectations.

The concept of user satisfaction can be explained in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Customer Satisfaction's Concept (Tjiptono, 2000)

3. Materials and Methods

Surveys, especially to agencies that organize public services to obtain data and information on: Service procedures; Requirements; Clarity of officers; Discipline of officers; Responsibilities of officers; Ability of officers; Speed of service; Justice in service; Courtesy and Hospitality Officer; Fairness and cost certainty; Certainty of service schedule; Environmental comfort and Safety service. Data collected from the service that provides direct service to the public.

Sample consists of:

People who enjoy / require public policies and services to be sampled on the basis of the nearest, medium, and farthest from the service center

- 1) Public sector organization that provides services to the public directly
- 2) Inspectorate as an external auditor

Data collection was done through questionnaires and in-depth interviews and limited group discussions. The collected data will be analyzed and create a system/ mechanism/ flow of monitoring and measurement of public satisfaction whether done by internal auditors, or external auditors. The development of monitoring and measurement system concept includes analysis of various aspects needed for the improvement of monitoring system and measurement of public satisfaction with the concept of Quality Control performed by Public sector organization.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Public Sector Organization

Sample public sector organization is public sector that performs administrative service which are Civil Registry Office; Industry, Trade and Cooperative Office, and Regional Investment Office. Civil Registry Offices issuing civil registration letters such as birth certificates, deaths, marriages, divorces, and so forth. As a reference for the implementation of services, among others are Enactment No. 23 of 2006 and Regional Regulation No. 42 of 2002. In implementing the public service it is felt that the relationship between the equivalent institutions related to public services has not been well coordinated. Currently, equivalent institutions such as the Ministry of Religious Affairs, the Office of Religious Affairs, and the District Court are still on their own. The results of surveys on the public that have been accepted for example such as Population Identity Number, and Family Card have been responded by conducting socialization to various institutions such as schools, sub-districts, and even in electronic media and newspapers. In maintaining the continuity of service there has been no quality control group. The standard of service performed refers to the regulation such as the settlement of affairs within 2 days and the delay in 10 days. Public expectations are now accommodated through a suggestion box or complaints via phone. Service shall be deemed satisfactory if it has been carried out in accordance with the terms and conditions set forth in the regional regulations. To maintain the quality and improve service in this service has been done tiered supervision from the head of the public sector – vice public sector to staff. The current system can not accommodate complaints and know the expectations of the public this is because the ability of human resources in carrying out public services has not been evenly distributed.

Industry, Trade and Cooperative Office which provides services of Trade Business License, Service Registration License and Industrial Business License also there is making permission of cooperative legal entity. Industry, Trade and Cooperative Office has never experienced obstacles in the implementation of public services. The classic obstacles occur usually only around the completeness of public administration, and there are some of them who want to get fast service. In dealing with this, usually public sector organization socializes the procedures applicable or the authorization to perform services. Service factors considered to be satisfactory to the public if the implementation is in accordance with applicable local regulations and Standard Operating Procedures and may exceed the target revenue area. Because public sector organization products emphasize the process, the right way to measure people's satisfaction according to them is by providing clear, timely and efficient information, time and cost. To monitor the satisfaction of public, Industry, Trade and Cooperative Office has conducted investor meetings.

Regional Investment Office shall provide Licensing Service of Business Place permit. Barriers commonly encountered in implementing services include lack of requirements from applicants, land status is not clear. Complaints from the public are almost nonexistent so it has never been thought of to respond to complaints.

4.2. Experience of Using Balance Score Card

Public managers have a number of programs to influence people and change the organization, but can not be used effectively without having a clear mission, value, vision and overall strategy. (Poister and Streib, 1999) Balanced Scorecard can be applied by non-profit organizations because it connects the gap between mission statement and blurred strategy and daily operational actions. BS facilitates organizational processes to achieve strategic focus, avoiding pathology trying to be everything to everyone. BS helps organizations avoid the illusions they have strategy because they manage a diverse and non-cumulative set programs and initiatives. (Kaplan, 2001). The Government of Palembang has been using Balance Score Card. The BSC has been placed in Bappeda as a pilot project since 2000. The public capability measurement system desired by public sector organization basically emphasizes two main aspects:

- 1) Emphasize on the process, in the sense of public satisfaction should really have been reflected from the start of the service process. From this aspect, it is seen that the simplification of requirement is very influencing the satisfaction of society from the process.
- 2) Emphasize on results, in the sense of public satisfaction can be measured by seeing whether the simplification of requirements completeness, and simplification of procedures will result in the rapid process of service. The size that can be used is to compare the standard that has been set against the number of days of service provision.

To implement the system of measurement and public satisfaction can form the structure in figure 2. as follows:

Figure 2: Organization chart for public satisfaction's measurement system

Given that there is no quality assurance in the Government of Palembang, it is necessary to consider whether a special team will be formed that will implement this function or simply by adding this new function to existing task groups in each public sector organization. For the public sector organization that will carry out customer satisfaction's measurement and create public satisfaction measurement system that appropriate to be implemented in each office, can adjust the type of services and methods to be used. So that, in the next stage system and size can be implemented on each public sector organization.

4.3. Parties Involved in Measuring Public Satisfaction

Public satisfaction on public sector services lies on in front-line officers. According to Bellou (2007), aggressiveness, decisiveness, innovativeness, age and rewards and outcome orientation denote factors effect on public employee's performance.

Some position involved in measure customer satisfaction are:

- 1) Quality inspector may be an internal or external auditor that involves the inspectorate: checking and ensuring that the services provided by the public sector organization are in compliance with minimum standards services.
- 2) Customer Charter contains the rights and obligations of society, punishment if officers do not fulfill the obligations, vision, mission and goals of the organization
- 3) Customer Service Standard made public sector organization
- 4) Customer redress: giving compensation to public
- 5) Quality quarantee: guarantee provided by the public sector organization in providing services
- 6) Customer information system: providing information to the public
- 7) Customer complaint system: contains the ways in which the public complains, what is the complaint, where / with whom the complaint is filed, how the complaint follow-up

The level of public satisfaction with service is an important factor in developing a service delivery system that is responsive to public needs, minimizing cost and time and maximizing service impacts on target populations. In order to develop a service delivery mechanism that meets the needs, wishes and expectations of the public, it is necessary to know the following;

- 1) Know what the public thinks about you, the services of the officers
- 2) Measuring and improving officer performance especially related to service ethics.
- 3) Build internal communication rides so everyone knows what they are doing.
- 4) Demonstrate your commitment to quality and society

4.4. Stages of Measuring the Level of Public Satisfaction

4.4.1. Data Collection

Identify the type of service, who provides the service and to whom the service is provided. This survey can utilize primary data from the community based on various socio-economic and geographical characteristics that include basic administrative services, basic infrastructure services and utilities, basic social services, and basic economic support.

Identify Service Performance. The issues discussed are in accordance with the expectations of the community such as the need for professionalism of officers, timeliness, ease of contact, the ability to solve problems and facilities owned in providing services.

Select respondents at random. Keep each respondent can represent various characteristics. Identify the community that will be the respondent. For example:

- 1) respondents based on location of residence: (far/ near from service location)
- 2) respondents based on the level of knowledge/ education (this is necessary to know the expected level of respondents)
- 3) respondents by sex: (difference in treatment of elderly respondents, pregnant women)
- 4) respondents based on income level/ economic strata, etc.

Or, it could be a survey conducted by the method of proportional random sampling. Sample sampling as follows:

The research was conducted to spread in the sub-district by taking into account the social, economic, cultural and geographical variations of the region. For example, in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample allocation based on area

No	District	Characteristic
1	Iilir Barat I	Residential area
2	Iilir Barat II	Trading area
3	Sako	Residential area
4	Gandus	Suburbs area
5	Plaju	Trading area
6	Seberang Ulu II	Residential area
7	Kawasan Kertapati	Trading area and Residential area
8	Seberang Ulu I	Residential area

Then the respondent data is taken from the population in the year when the research will be done, then selected population with age/ age > 20 years. Then for each sub-district can be sampled in accordance with the ability of each survey (viewed from time, the number of surveyed teams and

funds available). Questionnaires used as a tool survey. According to Pizam and Ellis (1999), questionnaires should be distributed throughout seven days of the week so that both weekdays and weekends are included. All questionnaires should be coded in advance for date.

4.5. Analytical Methods for Reporting Community Satisfaction

The importance of quality services is now very conscious. Service-based organizations are required to pay attention to service excellence in strategy and planning. Dimensions of service quality and measurement tools developed. The most widely used instrument to assess. Service quality is SERVQUAL. Several modifications and potential improvements to this measurement procedure have been suggested but the proposed new method has not been tested or proven to provide more accurate data in empirical studies. (Lewis and Mitchell; 1990)

Compile the numbers of people's satisfaction assessments on: (a) the level of service importance by the community, and (b) the performance of Servants in providing services, according to the factors agreed to be measured. The analysis can be based on the Decree of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment. Conduct a descriptive analysis of each answer collected in each variable. Matters included in the variables include:

- 1) Quality of Public Service, namely the quality of services provided by the government to the public, whose indicators include:
 - a) Direct evidence (Tangibles): is physical evidence that can be seen directly by permit applicants that may affect the quality of service, including: service room facilities; office supplies; officers and means of communication.
 - b) Reliability: the ability to provide promptly; accurately promised service; ability to provide satisfactory service; covering the immediate and accurate services that officers provide to the public. Officers who are able to provide satisfactory service to the community.
 - c) Responsiveness: The willingness of the officials to help the community; provide responsive service; includes officers with sincere intent to help the community; officers who are responsive in providing services in accordance with the wishes of the community.
 - d) Assurance: Ability; courtesy; credibility; legal certainty; so as to be free of any risk or hesitation that the officer is aware of.
 - e) Empathy: Ease of connecting with officers; able to communicate well; officers can understand the needs of the community.
- 2) Satisfaction of the Community, is the satisfaction of the recipient of the service, with the indicator of community satisfaction index as follows: Service procedure; Terms of Service; Clarity of Service Officers; Service Officers; Responsibilities of Service Officers; Service Officers Capacity; Service Speed; Courtesy and Friendliness of Officers; Fairness of Service Cost; Certainty of Service Cost; Certainty of Service Schedule; Environmental Comfort, and Security of Service.

Moynihan and Pandey (2007), research about the role of socio-historical context. The results show that public service has a very strong and positive motivation associated with the level education and membership in professional organizations. There is also a significant influence of organizational institutions, indicating that the red tape and length of organizational membership

are negatively related to the motivation of public service, while the hierarchical nature of authority and reform has a positive relationship. Public organizations have the opportunity and responsibility to create an environment that allows employees to be motivated that they contribute to the public good.

Christensen and Læg Reid (2005), found that first, public confidence in government is common: high levels of trust in institutions tend to extend to other institutions. Second, the variables of cultural politics have a strong influence on public trust in the government. The most important factor is the general satisfaction of democracy. Third, citizens who are satisfied with certain public services generally have higher levels of trust than dissatisfied citizens. Fourth, confidence in government is influenced by demographic factors, such as age, education and employment.

Other indicators that can be used are:

For product-oriented services. The measurements are:

- Effectiveness: the achievement of goals in the form of targets, long-term goals or mission public sector organization
- Productivity: the city government's ability to produce the products needed by the community
- Efficiency: municipal government produces service products with minimal cost and time
- Satisfaction: the extent to which the municipal government can meet the needs of employees and society
- Fairness: the extent of service should be as far and wide as possible

For process-oriented service products. The measurements are:

- Responsiveness: the responsiveness of public sector organizations to the expectations, desires, aspirations and demands of society
- Responsibility: conformity between service provision and existing law/ regulation
- Accountability: conformity between service delivery and external measures in society such as values/ norms
- Adaptability: responsiveness to change
- Survival: the city government's ability to grow
- Openness/ transparency: inform the community
- Empathy: the City Government's attention to issues that are developing in the community.

4.6. Baseline and Advanced Survey

When it comes to comparing data over time - to measure changes in the level of community satisfaction - do several times the same survey. Usually, do a baseline survey and follow-up survey. This is in accordance with the principle of continuous improvement so that the service will be improved according to the public assessment. The time interval between the two surveys depends on the purpose of the survey and also the readiness of the public sector organization just can not be too long. This can be done continuously, periodically, or at the beginning and end of the year.

Interpretation

To know public satisfaction can be done by measuring it. To be able to know to what extent the service has been able to meet the expectations or can provide services to the public, the organization must know the level of public expectations or a particular attribute. This public expectation will then be compared with the actual performance, so from here will be obtained index of public satisfaction that reflects the quality of service received by public. Public satisfaction data can be analyzed based on each service or welfare level, depending on the level of interest and desire of the evaluation team. Analysis can be done to compare the level of community public satisfaction based on: - Service to service; - Baseline and follow-up studies; and - the beginning of the year and the end of the year. The results section should provide details of all of the experiments that are required to support the conclusions of the paper. The section may be divided into subsections, each with a concise subheading.

It is advised that this section be written in past tense. It is a good idea to rely on charts, graphs, and tables to present the information. This way, the author is not tempted to discuss any conclusions derived from the study. The charts, graphs, and table should be clearly labeled and should include captions that outline the results without drawing any conclusions. A description of statistical tests as it relates to the results should be included.

Basically, all public sector organization that become the object of research keep trying to increase the satisfaction of its people through:

- 1) Conduct Self Evaluation as an effort to improve the service
- 2) Carry out effective consultations between internal departments in public sector organization.
- 3) Coordinate with other public sector organization in providing services to public.
- 4) Reward and punishment for the service provider's gaze as a form of appreciation for the success/ achievement of work that has been done, or a reprimand/ punishment for mistakes in the provision of services to public.
- 5) Conducting a survey of public satisfaction
- 6) Involve third parties directly related to service improvement efforts, either from a technical point of view, acceleration of completion time, or simplification of procedures, and requirements that must be equipped to obtain services
- 7) Improving further coordination with the inspectorate as a paying institution that can be used as a guide in carrying out monitoring and measuring public satisfaction
- 8) Completion of service implementing competencies, support equipment, and communications to public such as the socialization of service programs implemented by their respective public sector organization to improve the services provided.
- 9) Preparation of guidebooks or modules of public monitoring and measurement system as basic guidelines that can be operationalized
- 10) Create follow-up rules in the form of rewards or sanctions (sentences/ punishments) for public sector organizations that not perform well.

There is a tendency of each public sector organization to create a system of monitoring and measurement of public satisfaction based on internal constraints as well as external constraints faced by each public sector organization. In general, monitoring system and measuring public satisfaction are generally desired ranging from the simplest to the specific and technical.

Technical issues such as: Provider of suggestion box/ complaint box; Formation of a Quality Control cluster; Conducting Internal and External Audits; Develop a close relationship with consumers; Involving Technical Personnel in the front office as an effort to support the technical operational of each public sector organization in an effort to maximize the public satisfaction and meet the public directly to see any complaints.

5. Conclusions

In current state, several public sector organizations that have been surveyed it was found that there is no Monitoring System and Measurement public Satisfaction. Actually, measurement of Public Satisfaction has been done although not sustainable. Monitoring of public satisfaction is held by Inspectorate. It takes the legal power to make the monitoring system and the measurement of the public satisfaction that has been generated to be implemented by the public sector organization that exists within Government of Palembang City. As a strengthening of the legal basis, a Mayor's Decree is required.

References

- [1] Andaleeb, S. S. (2001). Service quality perceptions and patient satisfaction: a study of hospitals in a developing country. *Social science & medicine*, 52(9), 1359-1370.
- [2] Bellou, V. (2007). Achieving long-term customer satisfaction through organizational culture: Evidence from the health care sector. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 17(5), 510-522.
- [3] Christensen, T., & Læg Reid, P. (2005). Trust in government: The relative importance of service satisfaction, political factors, and demography. *Public Performance & Management Review*, 28(4), 487-511.
- [4] Fitrihana, Noor, Metode Pengumpulan Data dan Evaluasi dalam Pengendalian Kualitas, URL: <http://hadisugito.fadla.or.id/>, Mengukur Kepuasan Masyarakat, Download 8 Januari 2008 Jam 05.56
- [5] Kaplan, R. S. (2001). Strategic performance measurement and management in nonprofit organizations. *Nonprofit management and Leadership*, 11(3), 353-370.
- [6] Kotler, Philip, (1986). *Principles Of Marketing*, Englewood Cliffs, USA, Prentice Hall
- [7] Lewis, B. R., & Mitchell, V. W. (1990). Defining and measuring the quality of customer service. *Marketing intelligence & planning*, 8(6), 11-17.
- [8] Moynihan, D. P., & Pandey, S. K. (2007). The role of organizations in fostering public service motivation. *Public administration review*, 67(1), 40-53.
- [9] Pizam, A., & Ellis, T. (1999). Customer satisfaction and its measurement in hospitality enterprises. *International journal of contemporary hospitality management*, 11(7), 326-339.
- [10] Poister, T. H., & Streib, G. D. (1999). Strategic management in the public sector: Concepts, models, and processes. *Public Productivity & Management Review*, 308-325.
- [11] Ratminto, Atik Septi Winarsih. (2006). *Manajemen Pelayanan*, Pustaka Pelajar, Yogyakarta, 2006
- [12] Tjiptono, Fandi, dan Anastasia Diana. (1998). *Total Quality Management*, Penerbit Andi Offset, Yogyakarta
- [13] Tjiptono, Fandi. (2004). *Manajemen Pemasaran Jasa*, Penerbit Andi Offset, Yogyakarta
- [14] Yamit, Zulian. (2002). *Manajemen Kualitas Produk dan Jasa*, Ekonisia, Yogyakarta
- [15] Zeithml, Valarie A, A. Parasuraman, and Leonard, L. Berry. (1990). *Delivering Quality Services, Balancing Customer Perceptions and Expectations*, New York, USA, The Free Press

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